

101132933 – AD-RIDDLE

Real-World Implementation, Deployment and Validation of Early Detection Tools and Lifestyle Enhancement

WP2 – Real-World Testing of Digital Cognitive Assessments

D2.2 Study initiation package: Core protocol with all sub-studies for digital cognitive assessments

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V2.1	24 JUN 2025	Final Draft for Internal Review with Feedback
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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the AD-RIDDLE Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

RS: Region Stockholm, Karolinska Universitetssjukhuset – Sweden (**The Coordinator**)

KI: Karolinska Institutet, Department of Neurobiology, Care Sciences and Society – Sweden

FBHI: Stiftelsen Fingers Brain Health Institute – Sweden

UGOT: Goteborgs Universitet – Sweden

ULUND: Lunds Universitet – Sweden

UEF: Itä-Suomen Yliopisto, University of Eastern Finland – Finland

AUMC: Stichting Amsterdam UMC – The Netherlands

UM: Universiteit Maastricht – The Netherlands

BBRC: Fundació Barcelonaβeta Brain Research Center – Spain

SYNAPSE: Synapse Research Management Partners S.L – Spain

AE: Alzheimer Europe – Luxembourg

ADI: Alzheimer’s Disease International – United States

UNIPG: Università Degli Studi di Perugia – Italy

GV: Gates Ventures LLC – United States (**The Co-Coordinator**)

COMBINOSTICS: Combinostics Oy – Finland

Fujirebio: Fujirebio Europe NV – Belgium

SARD: Sanofi-Aventis Recherche & Development – France

C2N: C2N Diagnostics LLC – United States

neotiv GmbH: Neotiv GmbH – Germany

CCL: Cambridge Cognition Limited – United Kingdom

DAVOS: Davos Alzheimer’s Collaborative – United States

VGR: VÄSTRA GÖTALANDSREGIONEN – Sweden

ULEIC: University of Leicester – United Kingdom

ICL: Imperial College of Science, Technology and medicine – United Kingdom

NICE: National Institute for Health and Care Excellence – United Kingdom

SUS: SANOFI US Services Inc – United States

SADG: SANOFI-AVENTIS Deutschland GMBH – Germany

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IHI for the undertaking of the AD-RIDDLE project (101132933).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The AD-RIDDLE Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst AD-RIDDLE participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties’ obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Deliverable 2.2. describes the core protocol including sub-studies for real-world testing piloting the digital cognitive assessments (DCAs) as described and identified in in D2.1 (Task 2.2). This is the first step towards the larger scale real-world testing (Task 2.3). The core protocol for pilot testing has been developed collaboratively with all WP2 members, including relevant site leads and the industry partners contributing DCAs. Based on WP2 discussions, AUMC (WP2 lead) drafted the core protocol which was then shared with the participating clinical sites to enable adjustments to their site-specific situation. Study initiation activities include demo sessions for each DCA, standardized operation procedures (SOPs) for all study procedures and DCAs, and 1-on-1 training sessions with the AUMC team and each clinical site. Further, a WP2 training and technical assistance (TTA) forum has been created, which is led by the AUMC team and meets on a bi-weekly-to-weekly basis. While preparing the pilot study, we simultaneously worked on aligning with WPs 3, 4 and 5 to develop the large-scale validation study in a core clinical protocol (CCP). Based on the steps, we continue to finalize preparations for successful rollout of the larger-scale testing in Task 2.3. As such, this Deliverable provides the groundwork for successful execution of the WP2 large-scale validation study across each of the clinical sites and in alignment with WP3,4 and 5.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Alzheimer’s disease (AD) requires innovative approaches for early detection and prevention. Compared with standard paper-and-pencil testing, digital cognitive assessment (DCA) tools have great potential due to their higher sensitivity to early disease and better ecological validity. Additionally, by removing the need for individuals to travel for their cognitive assessment(s), sensitive, specific, and valuable cognitive measures could be captured on a large scale with ease, while offering greater cost-efficiencies, accessibility, and data aggregation (Van den Berg et al. JMIR, 2025).

The overall goal of AD-RIDDLE Work Package 2 is to conduct real-world testing of validated and novel/exploratory DCAs to improve early AD detection and prediction of cognitive decline and dementia. Crucial for successful real-life testing is optimal implementation of digital tools in daily practice. Despite rapid useful developments in AI, remote testing and digital tools, there is a gap when considering validation and implementation in memory-clinics and community-based settings. Overall, stakeholders, e.g., patients, caregivers and health-care professionals, are highly positive towards the use of digital tools, yet also point out that there are challenges to actually integrate and use digital tools in routine care practices (Van Gils et al. JMIR, 2011). Thus, a careful selection of DCAs as well as pilot testing these selected tools in a real-world setting is needed to prepare for larger scale testing and moving towards sustainable implementation.

We aim to achieve this by addressing the following key objectives:

- **Task 2.1:** Prepare the real-world testing i.e., optimize validated DCAs with input from relevant stakeholders; provide clinical sites with a library of operational and culturally relevant digital tools;
- **Task 2.2:** Conduct a pilot study to determine feasibility and usability of DCAs;
- **Task 2.3:** Conduct a large-scale study testing DCAs (in combination with blood-based biomarkers) in real-world settings across the patient journey;
- **Task 2.4:** Perform data analyses using mixed methods, integrating quantitative and qualitative data.

The current report describes the Core Protocol for real-world testing piloting the DCAs as identified in 2.1, as well as the ongoing preparatory steps towards the larger scale real-world testing in T2.3.

2. CORE PROTOCOL FOR PILOTING DIGITAL COGNITIVE ASSESSMENTS

The initial plan was to conduct a pilot test at three sites; however, due to strong interest from all sites, the protocol has been revised to include participation from all eight clinical sites. The approach described therefore pertains to the core protocol that will be implemented in each participating clinical site. Briefly:

- The core protocol for pilot testing was developed collaboratively with all WP2 members, including relevant site leads and the industry partners contributing to the DCAs as identified in D2.1.
- AUMC (WP2 lead) drafted the core protocol for pilot testing, which was then shared with the participating clinical sites to enable adjustments to their site-specific implementation. Each clinical site submits their protocol to their local IRB.

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2.1. Study Objectives

The main objectives of the pilot study are to:

1. Evaluate feasibility and usability of the different DCAs in the spectrum of cognitive decline and Alzheimer’s disease.
2. Harmonize different DCAs by correlating to each other and to standardized paper-and-pencil cognitive tests.

2.2. Study Participants

We include participants from memory clinics or general population with known cognitive status (normal cognition or subjective cognitive decline (SCD), a diagnosis of mild cognitive impairment (MCI) or (mild) AD dementia). Each site aims to enrol n=20-30 participants (e.g., n=10 SCD, n=10 MCI and n=10 mild AD dementia at one site, but distribution may differ according to local circumstances), aiming to reach a total of N=150.

2.2.1. Inclusion criteria

- Willing and able to provide informed consent.
- 40 years or older.
- Access to and experience with a touchscreen-based device.
- Able to read and speak the local language.
- Have MoCA score ≥ 11 points or MMSE score ≥ 19 points
- Can identify a study partner who is an adult, has ongoing contact with the participant, and is willing and able to sign the study partner informed consent.

2.2.2. Exclusion criteria

- Significant neurological, psychiatric or other conditions (e.g. hearing or vision impairment) hindering ability to complete study procedures, based on clinical judgement.
- Impaired decision-making capacity that renders the individual incapable of consenting or completing study assessments, based on clinical judgement.

2.3. Study Design

This study has a cross-sectional, group (between)*DCA (within) design. Participants will undergo a standardized paper-and-pencil cognitive assessment and one digital assessment in the clinic, followed by remote digital cognitive assessments at home (in random order), with 1-week intervals (Figure 1).

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Figure 1: Overview of the Pilot Study design.

2.4. Study Outcome Measurements

2.4.1. Digital Cognitive Assessments

Digital cognitive Assessments are:

- *Cambridge Neuropsychological Test Automated Battery (CANTAB, partner: CCL)*. CANTAB includes highly sensitive, precise and objective measures of cognitive function, correlated to neural networks. CANTAB tests have demonstrated sensitivity to detecting changes in neuropsychological performance. The subtests used for this pilot are Paired Associates Learning (PAL), Spatial Working Memory (SWM) and Digit Symbol Substitution test (DST). Duration: 17 minutes. (Robbins, 1994).
 - Primary outcome measure is a z-score generated for key measures from the tasks.
- *cCOG (partner: COMBINOSTICS)*. Self-administered battery on memory, speed, attention, visuospatial, and executive functioning. Correlates with traditional paper-and-pencil test and differentiates between healthy controls, MCI and dementia, and between AD and different types of dementia. Duration: 20 minutes.
 - Primary outcome measure is a global cognition score based on the different features.
- *Neotiv (partner: neotiv GmbH)*. Digital platform to enable the remote assessment and monitoring of cognitive impairment along the Alzheimer’s disease (AD) continuum. Consisting of novel, anatomically validated tests for the remote and unsupervised assessment of episodic memory: 1) the Mnemonic Discrimination Task for Objects and Scenes (MDT-OS); 2) the Object-in-Room Recall test

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(ORR); and 3) the Complex Scene Recognition test (CSR). Duration: three tests (15-20 minutes) , resulting in a total administration time of ~50 minutes.

- Primary outcome measure is a remote digital memory composite (RDMC) score derived from the z-scores of the three individual tests.

- *BioCog (partner: ULUND)*. Self-administered cognitive assessment battery. It includes a wordlist test with immediate and delayed recall, a modified Symbol Digit Modalities Test, orientation to time, Trail Making Tests A and B, and a paired associates test. The test battery is divided into two parts: the first part takes approximately 10 minutes to complete, and the second part takes an additional 15 minutes, totalling 25 minutes.
 - Primary outcome measure is a global score based on the score in the subtests.

- *Amsterdam IADL Questionnaire (partner: AUMC)*. Questionnaire completed by a study partner of the patient (e.g., spouse, friend, or relative). Targets functional impairment in cognitively complex daily activities, e.g., handling finances, using everyday technology. Extensively validated for use in (preclinical) AD and related disorders (reliability, diagnostic use, content and construct validity, and clinical meaningfulness). Duration: 10 minutes. (Jutten, 2017).
 - Primary outcome measure is a total T-score generated, normally distributed with a mean of 50 and a standard deviation (SD) of 10 in a memory clinic population. Scores range from approximately 20–80, with higher scores representing better daily functioning.

2.4.2. Paper-and-pencil tests

Study parameters for **paper-and-pencil** cognitive tests are:

- *Mini-mental state examination (MMSE)*. Measures orientation, verbal memory registration and short delayed recall, working memory, language, and visuospatial abilities, scoring range 0-30. (Folstein et al., 1975). Duration: 10 minutes.
- *Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA)*. Brief cognitive test designed to assess mild cognitive impairment (MCI). The time to administer the MoCA test is approximately 10 min and has a maximum of 30 points. (Nasreddine et al. 2005).
- *Repeatable Battery for Assessment of Neuropsychological Status (RBANS)*. The 12 items on the RBANS assess five cognitive domains: immediate memory, visuospatial/constructional abilities, language, attention, and delayed memory. Total scores show a possible range of 40–160. (Randolph, 1998). Duration: 30 minutes.
- *Preclinical Alzheimer Cognitive Composite (PACC-5)*. The PACC-5 is a widely used cognitive outcome measure in research and clinical trials of preclinical AD and comprises well-validated paper-and-pencil tests. The PACC-5 is computed as an averaged z-score of all individual measures. (Donohue et

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al., 2014; Papp et al., 2017). Depending on site-specific availability of the individual PACC-5 tests, a modified PACC-5 may be derived (Mattsson-Carlgrén et al., 2023). Duration: 25 minutes.

2.5. Study Endpoints

Feasibility of the different DCAs in the spectrum of cognitive decline and AD will focus on the following aspects of recruitment and retention:

- Ease of onboarding as measured by clinician’s and participants experience (visual analogue scale)
- Number of invited eligible individuals who accept to participate in the study (i.e. sign the informed consent form)
- Number of participants who complete each DCA (percentage calculated as number of participants who complete each DCA divided by total number of participants).
- Number of participants that contact the study team for support (through phone calls or email). (percentage calculated as total number of contacts divided by total number of participants per DCA randomization order)

Usability of the different DCAs in the spectrum of cognitive decline and AD will be evaluated using the System Usability Scale (SUS), a ten-item scale giving a global view of subjective assessments of usability (Brooke, 1996) in digital format (integrated at the end of each DCA).

Harmonization of the different DCAs will be done by correlating them to each other and to paper-and-pencil tests. Scoring range and scores of each DCA will also be compared between clinical diagnostic groups (normal/SCD, MCI, mild AD dementia).

2.6. Data management plan

Encrypted and coded data will be uploaded to a central database accommodated by Castor EDC (AUMC) within an environment specifically created for sharing with and exclusively to research partners within this project. The participant ID includes an identifier for the clinical site from which the participant are recruited. Additionally, two descriptive variables are included in the dataset to indicate the 1) care setting as well as 2) specific service organization within each care setting from which participants are recruited. Agreements about data sharing across sites and industry partners participating in the pilot study were laid out in a Data Annex, which was approved during the WP2 meeting dd. May 9th, 2025.

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3. STUDY SITES AND RECRUITMENT SOURCES

The pilot study will be conducted in all eight WP2 clinical sites, in a memory-clinic, primary care or community-based setting (Table 1). As shown in Table 1, all DCAs will be assessed at each site. A detailed description of each site and recruitment source is provided below.

Table 1. Overview of pilot study sites and recruitment settings.								
	RS	UGOT	ULUND	AUMC	UEF	ICL	BBRC	UNIPG
	Memory-clinic	Memory-clinic and community-based	Primary care	Memory clinic	Community-based	Primary care	Primary care	Memory-clinic
cCog	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
NEotiv	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
CANTAB	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
BioCog	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
A-IADL-Q	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

✓ indicates that DCA will be pilot tested at that specific site.

3.1. Region Stockholm (RS) Sweden

Karolinska University Hospital, as part of Region Stockholm (RS), is one of the largest EU university hospitals, ranked highest in Europe and fifth worldwide. Medical Unit Aging has strong expertise on dementia diseases with large patient flows, Unit for Clinical Trials, and extensive experience with biomarker and other AD studies. It has also conducted several FINGER-based dementia prevention trials. Recently, it opened a Brain Health Clinic to facilitate early implementation of dementia prevention.

Karolinska University Hospital has two highly specialized Memory Clinics in Huddinge and Solna (total about 1000 new visits per year). Patients are referred from primary care in the catchment area. Specialized referrals include younger / working age patients from the entire Stockholm region, and familial cases from across Sweden and older patients with suspected dementia. About one third of evaluated patients receive a dementia diagnosis, and the rest have MCI / prodromal AD or subjective cognitive decline (SCD). Dementia work-up is conducted according to national guidelines, including basic work-up in primary care, and when indicated, extended work-up in a specialized memory clinic.

The real-world testing study will be conducted in a memory clinic setting, with potential to engage primary healthcare settings in prospective data collection.

3.2. Göteborgs universitet (UGOT), Sweden

Real-world testing will be conducted within the ongoing REAL AD study which leverages more than 110 primary care units across the Västra Götalandregion in Wester Sweden and has enrolled over 3000 active participants. Validation assessments and AD-RIDDLE pilot will be conducted in collaboration with the Sahlgrenska University Hospital Memory Clinic which is located at the Clinic for Neuropsychiatry and proves adequate testing space and medical examination rooms. The Clinical Core includes offices for staff and

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faculty, 8 medical examination rooms, rooms for clinical drug studies and ancillary study interviewing and a medical records room and a patient/caregiver waiting room. In addition, the facilities of the University of Gothenburg, Sahlgrenska Academy are located in the same building also on the fourth floor and are available to our staff. The space includes several testing/examination rooms, a social work interview room and reception/secretarial area. Central conference rooms are available. The clinical staff of the Memory clinic includes neuropsychologists, specialist nurses, PhD level neuropsychologist, social workers, occupational therapists and geriatric psychiatrists and neurologists. All Clinicians and staff participate in a weekly interdisciplinary clinical consensus conference, in which cognitive diagnoses for memory clinic patients are discussed. Every year, about 450 novel patients are seen.

3.3. Lunds Universitet (LU), Sweden

The Memory Clinic at Skåne University Hospital in Malmö is a leading centre for the assessment, diagnosis, and treatment of memory disorders and dementia. It provides services to both younger and older individuals experiencing cognitive symptoms. The clinic comprises a specialized memory unit, a mobile outpatient team, and a clinical drug trials unit.

It is closely affiliated with the Clinical Memory Research Unit at Lund University and serves as a central site for the Swedish BioFINDER study. Real-world pilot testing will be conducted within the BioFINDER Primary Care study, which recruits participants from 20 primary care centres across southern Sweden. Patients presenting with cognitive symptoms—either self-reported or reported by a relative—are eligible for inclusion. Following initial cognitive testing and clinical assessment by their primary care physician, patients are referred to the Malmö Memory Clinic for further evaluation.

The BioFINDER Primary Care study was launched in 2020 and has, to date, enrolled over 1,000 participants with subjective cognitive decline, mild cognitive impairment, or dementia.

3.4. Amsterdam UMC (AUMC), the Netherlands

Real-world pilot testing will be conducted in a memory clinic setting, specifically the memory clinic of Alzheimer Center Amsterdam. Alzheimer Center Amsterdam, part of the department of Neurology of Amsterdam UMC, is one of five Alzheimer Centres in the Netherlands. It has the mission to contribute to personalized medicine, with a focus on early onset dementia. Research lines include (i) finding the origin of the disease, (ii) diagnosis & prognosis, and (iii) intervention & prevention. All patients presenting at the memory clinic of Alzheimer Center Amsterdam (~500 new patients per year) are asked to provide informed consent for the use of their clinical data for research purposes. Together, they form the ongoing Amsterdam Dementia Cohort. Almost half of patients present with a type of dementia, 35% SCD or MCI, and a minority have another psychiatric or neurological disorder. Patients are referred from primary care (1/3) or from a local memory clinic (2/3 second opinions). Work-up is done in a standardized fashion.

3.5. University of Eastern Finland (UEF), Finland

The UEF Brain Research Unit (BRU) is one of the largest academic neurological clinical trial units in the Nordic countries, with experience since 1992 in dementia-related clinical studies. It has also conducted several FINGER-based dementia prevention trials. The UEF BRU has an accredited biomarker laboratory for neurodegenerative diseases, and since 2005 provides a national biomarker laboratory service available for physicians and hospitals (now also plasma NFL for clinical use).

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The UEF BRU works together with the highly specialized memory clinic at the Kuopio University Hospital Department of Neurology (up to 200 new patients per year), the regional referral centre for all people of working age or aged <75 years, and centre for genetic and rare/atypical cases in the entire Central and Eastern Finland region. People aged <75 years are referred from primary care (public) or occupational healthcare (private). People aged over 75 years are assessed in Geriatrics policlinics (primary care memory clinics), with referral to Neurology in specific cases.

A continuous recruitment platform for research studies connects UEF BRU with the Neurology memory clinic. The platform can replicate implementation in a real-world memory clinic environment, e.g. for tools not yet approved for routine clinical use. It can also potentially connect with Geriatrics policlinics in prospective data collection. The platform is a main contact point for people of all ages in the region interested in participation in dementia-related research.

3.6. Imperial College (ICL), UK

The Pilot Study will be conducted in the AGEing (AGE) Epidemiology Unit of the School of Public Health, Department of Medicine at Imperial College London. The research unit focuses on observational studies determining risk factors for Alzheimer’s Disease and in clinical intervention trials to prevent dementia and slow cognitive decline. Participants will be recruited from an observational, longitudinal study cohort, the Cognitive Health in Ageing Register: Investigational Observational and Trial Studies in Dementia Research: Prospective Readiness Cohort, CHARIOT-PRO, initiated in 2015 and now extended to the CHARIOT-PRO Longitudinal Study (CPLS) of older adults 60 years and over, cognitively healthy at initial study enrolment. Participants enrolled in CPLS now include those cognitively healthy and those with subjective cognitive decline (SCD) and mild cognitive impairment (MCI). All clinic visits for CPLS are conducted at the following location: Stadium House, 68 Wood Lane, London, W12 7RH based. There is secure access to building and AGE has secure storage for study documentation.

3.7. Barcelona Beta Brain Research Centre (BBRC), Spain

The Barcelonaβeta Brain Research Center (BBRC), the research institute of the Pasqual Maragall Foundation, focuses on Alzheimer’s disease prevention, particularly in its preclinical phase. Since 2012, BBRC has led pioneering longitudinal research supported by deeply phenotyped cohorts and biomarker analysis.

Its main research infrastructure is the ALFA study, a cohort of nearly 3,000 cognitively unimpaired individuals aged 45–75, primarily descendants of Alzheimer’s patients. Nested to the ALFA parent cohort, the BBRC established the longitudinal, long-term ALFA+ study in which a more detailed phenotyping is performed. ALFA+ is a prospective and observational cohort study for the early identification of biomarkers (both fluid and neuroimaging) of AD in ~420 cognitively unimpaired individuals. Another BBRC study cohort is the β-AARC study, which involves 200 participants experiencing cognitive decline. This study focuses on the early detection of AD related pathophysiological changes by analysing clinical, cognitive, imaging, and biomarker data from blood and cerebrospinal fluid.

The BBRC collaborates closely with the Memory Unit of the Department of Neurology at Hospital del Mar (Barcelona, Spain), facilitating direct recruitment of clinical cohorts and enabling translational research. This synergy, supported by the geographic proximity between BBRC and Hospital del Mar, allows the design and implementation of real-world-ready research platforms.

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3.8. University of Perugia (UNIPG), Italy

The real-world pilot study will be carried out within a memory clinic setting at the Center for Cognitive Disorders and Dementias, part of the Section of Gerontology and Geriatrics at the University of Perugia and Perugia University Hospital.

Established in 1984, our Center has long served as a national referral hub for neurocognitive disorders. Each year, we evaluate approximately 200 new patients referred from primary care or other memory clinics. We provide ongoing clinical follow-up for more than 180 individuals with subjective cognitive decline, over 600 patients diagnosed with mild cognitive impairment (MCI), and more than 700 individuals with major neurocognitive disorders. These patients are monitored regularly to assess disease progression, therapeutic efficacy, care strategies, and family support mechanisms.

The Center is highly active in both biological and clinical research, collaborating with numerous national and international centres of excellence. Recent research initiatives include participation in clinical trials investigating current pharmacological treatments for Alzheimer’s disease, as well as preventive interventions for cognitive decline, such as the Lethe study.

4. STUDY INITIATION ACTIVITIES

Study initiation activities include providing translations and demo sessions for DCAs for each clinical site, standardized operation procedures (SOPs), and 1-on-1 training sessions with the AUMC team and each clinical site. Further, a training and technical assistance (TTA) forum has been created, which is led by the AUMC team and meets on a weekly-to-biweekly basis.

4.1. Demo and training sessions DCAs

In collaboration with the developers of each digital cognitive assessment tool, we organized dedicated demo sessions for all participating clinical sites. These sessions introduced site teams to the functionalities, use cases, and best practices for each DCA platform. Recordings of these demonstrations and supporting training materials are accessible to project partners via the WP2 SharePoint folder.

4.2. Standard Operation Procedures (SOPs)

To ensure smooth and consistent implementation across all clinical sites, we developed clear and comprehensive SOPs. Table 2 provides an overview of SOPs and their content. All SOPs were written by the AUMC team and reviewed by the clinical sites. SOPs for DCAs were additionally reviewed by the relevant industry and academic parties (DCA developers). Altogether, these documents provide step-by-step guidance on every aspect of the participant journey and data handling process, facilitating standardized procedures across countries and sites and thereby promoting data quality.

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Table 2. Overview of SOPs created for the AD-RIDDLE Pilot Study.	
SOP Title	Description
Screening and recruitment	This SOP aims to describe the screening and recruitment that occur with participants to assess if they are appropriate and interested in participating in this study.
Participant ID & Randomisation	This SOP explains how to assign participant IDs and to randomize the order of the digital assessments for all sites.
On-site assessment	This SOP defines the method to complete the on-site assessment for the AD-RIDDLE pilot study. Including: pre-arrival tasks, on-site paper and pencil assessment, digital tool onboarding and on-site digital assessment.
Paper-and-pencil tests	This SOP defines the method to complete the paper & pencil tests during the on-site visit for the pilot study.
Digital test - BioCog	This SOP describes the procedure to handle the BioCog digital test for the AD-RIDDLE pilot study, including sending invitations to participants, preparation, and reviewing test results.
Digital test - CANTAB	This SOP describes the procedure to handle the CANTAB digital test for the AD-RIDDLE pilot study, including sending invitations to participants, preparation, administration, and reviewing test results.
Digital test - Neotiv	This SOP describes the procedure to handle the Neotiv digital test for the AD-RIDDLE pilot study, including sending invitations to participants, preparation, and reviewing test results.
Digital test - cCOG	This SOP describes the procedure to handle the cCOG digital test for the AD-RIDDLE pilot study, including sending invitations to participants, preparation, administration, and reviewing test results.
Digital test - A-IADL-Q	This SOP describes the procedure to handle the BioCOG digital test for the AD-RIDDLE pilot study, including sending invitations to participants' study partner, preparation, administration, and reviewing test results.
Data management and storage	This SOP aims to describe the procedure to handle data entry in Castor, and how and where to store (paper) data.
Travel reimbursement	This SOP outlines the process for reimbursing travel costs after a participant completes an in-clinic visit and requests reimbursement.
Debriefing call	This SOP describes the procedure for conducting debriefing calls with participants, including questions about their study experience.

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4.3. Training and Teaching Assistance

Within WP2, a training and technical assistance (TTA) forum has been created. This is a group of representatives from each clinical site, led by the Amsterdam team. The aim of this group is to address practical issues related both to drafting the protocol, initiating the study and providing training and technical assistance for real-world piloting the DCAs. During the pilot study preparation phase, the group met on a bi-weekly basis. Starting in June, the TTA group convenes on a weekly basis. These weekly sessions will follow step-by-step guide for implementation for each site, including key tools (such as SOPs, test materials), and sharing successful implementation strategies as well as known challenges. Altogether, the WP2 TTA group will provide a forum where site leaders can receive ongoing support for pilot testing the DCAs at their site, helping them address operational questions and build confidence in using the DCAs and the pilot study workflow. The WP2 group will also be linked to WP3, WP4 and WP5, as we develop the protocol for the large-scale validation study (see section 5).

5. LARGE-SCALE STUDY PROTOCOL DEVELOPMENT

While setting up the DCA pilot study, we simultaneously worked on aligning with WPs 3, 4 and 5 to develop the large-scale validation study in a core protocol. This has resulted in the Core Clinical Protocol (CCP), which provides an innovative integrated framework for two related sets of objectives across studies: validation of DCAs and BBMs as new tools for AD diagnostics (and exploratory prediction/prognosis), and evaluation of their implementation in real-world settings. Defining this integrated framework is crucial to bridge the current gap between AD diagnostic validation and implementation evaluation studies (Figure 2).

WP interdependencies in CCP

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Figure 2. Overview of AD-RIDDLE work packages (WPs) and interdependencies as described in the core clinical protocol (CCP).

The CCP provides harmonization guidelines for a set of real-world studies testing how DCAs and BBMs can be combined to adapt to various local settings in multiple countries. The CCP document outlines the main principles of harmonization of these real-world studies (Figure 3). Aspects covered include selection of study settings, study participants, DCAs and BBMs, and definitions of outcomes. The document also outlines main elements of data collection and harmonization, and principles of data sharing and pooled data-analyses.

Figure 3. Real-world testing of DCAs and BBMs: overview of main objectives as described in the CCP.

5.1. WP2 large-scale validation study of DCAs

For WP2 specifically, the primary objectives of the large-scale validation study are to:

1. Assess concordance between DCAs and clinical diagnosis
2. Investigate change over time on DCAs (by clinical diagnostic group)

Recruitment will take place across general populations, primary care settings, and/or memory clinics. The estimated total sample size across all participating sites is up to 20,000 participants. These participants will undergo repeated digital cognitive assessments over a period of up to three years, which may include the piloting stage (Table 3). This initiative will be closely aligned with WP3 (BBM) and WP5 (implementation evaluation), with each site expected to recruit approximately 200 participants who will complete both the DCA and BBM components and additionally have AD pathology reference standard (CSF or amyloid PET) available from routine memory clinic assessments.

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	Pilot study*	Large-scale testing studies	
		Baseline assessment	Follow-up assessment (12, 24, 36 months)
Informed consent	X	X	(X)
Digital cognitive assessment(s)	X	X	X (Yearly)
Clinical Dx	X	X	X (Optional)
Demographics (Age, sex, education)	X	X	X
Digital skills questions	X	X	N.A.
Digital participant-reported measures (e.g., lifestyle-related, medical history)	N.A.	X	N.A.
**BBMs	X	X	X (once at the end of study, sub-sample as per site appendix)
Standard neuropsychological tests	X	<i>According to local routine practice</i>	
Imaging biomarkers	N.A.		
CSF biomarkers	N.A.		
Other investigations	N.A.		

**Participants in the pilot study may continue directly into the large-scale study. **BBMs for pilot study if available at local site. BBMs in large-scale testing as per WP3 protocol.*

5.1.1 Eligibility criteria

Inclusion and exclusion criteria are largely similar to those used in the pilot study. As such, participants in the pilot study may continue directly into the large-scale study.

Inclusion criteria

- Age range 40+ years (no upper limit)
- Willing and able to provide informed consent
- Able to read and speak the local language (site-specific)
- It is preferable (but not compulsory) that the participants can identify a study partner who is an adult, has ongoing contact with the participant, and is willing and able to sign the study partner informed consent.

Exclusion criteria

- Significant neurological, psychiatric or other conditions (e.g. hearing or vision impairment) hindering ability to complete study procedures according to clinical judgement.

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- Impaired decision-making capacity that renders the individual incapable of consenting or completing study assessments, based on clinical judgement.

Additional eligibility criteria (described in deliverable D3.1) will be applied to participants who also provide blood samples for BBMs, in alignment with WP3.

5.1.2 Study initiation activities

Relevant SOPs from the pilot study (Table 2) are also being adapted at each study site for the larger-scale testing. During pilot study preparations, the study sites have also started preparations for the site-specific larger-scale DCAs implementation.

6. DISCUSSION

This report outlines the core protocol and objectives for piloting digital cognitive assessments (DCAs) as part of real-world testing in the context of cognitive decline and Alzheimer’s disease. The pilot study aims to evaluate the feasibility and usability of multiple DCAs across different stages of cognitive impairment and to harmonize these digital tools by comparing them with traditional paper-and-pencil tests. A total of at least 150 participants will be recruited across eight AD-RIDDLE clinical sites. Each site is expected to enrol 20–30 participants with a mix of SCD, MCI or mild AD dementia.

To ensure standardized implementation, comprehensive standard operating procedures (SOPs) have been developed, covering all aspects from recruitment to data management. Site teams received demos and training for each DCA, with ongoing support provided through regular meetings and one-on-one sessions. Additionally, within WP2 a TTA forum has been created. As described in 4.3., the WP2 TTA activities focus mainly on study preparation and initiation for successful pilot testing of the DCAs at each site, whereas implementation evaluation activities are more concentrated in WP5.

Of note, the initial plan was to conduct a pilot test at only three sites; however, due to great interest from all sites it was decided to include all eight clinical sites in the pilot study. Therefore, the protocol has been revised to include participation from all eight clinical sites. As such, comprehensive preparations for the core protocol for both pilot and larger-scale testing have been conducted simultaneously. We already have approval for 4 clinical sites (AUMC, UNIPG, ULUND, UEF), which are now ready for pilot recruitment. We expect to have IRB approval in most other sites by July 2025. Data collection for the large-scale validation can start taking place in parallel, hence we do not expect large deviations from timelines.

The CCP describing the large-scale validation studies with harmonization guidelines across WPs enables a set of real-world studies testing DCAs and BBMs in diverse settings, from application in the general population, to primary care and memory clinics. It also enables integration of *diagnostic validation* and *implementation evaluation* objectives to facilitate increased use in practice. It is important to emphasize that AD-RIDDLE real-world testing is not a single study with multiple European sites and one centralized protocol to be strictly and uniformly applied at all sites. A one-size-fits-all approach does not recognize that health-care systems (HCS)

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will have differing needs and preferences. Thus, the CCP enables a more customized approach in which sites can choose from DCA and BBM options to suit their needs. For example, depending on regulatory requirements or HCS preference, one DCA tool may be preferable over another; one blood biomarker test may be incompatible with one setting yet be priority in another. As such, sites will have flexibility to assemble the set of ‘tools’ that are right for them. However, to ensure that cross site analyses can be conducted, some common data requirements will be applied. We are currently working on finalizing these requirements, in close collaboration with each clinical site and in alignment with the other work packages.

7. CONCLUSION

This Deliverable provides the groundwork for successful execution of the WP2 large-scale validation study of DCAs across each of the clinical sites. Ultimately, validated and easily accessible DCAs and blood-based biomarkers will enable patients with preclinical or prodromal Alzheimer’s disease to receive a timely diagnosis and be directed towards personalized therapies to prevent or delay dementia onset.